

Figure 3d: the 5x5 funerary vāstu, PI 8.248-255b.

1	earth	6	Carakī	10	Skanda
2	water	7	Vidārī	11	Aryaman
3	fire	8	Pūtanā	12	Jambha
4	air	9	Pāparākṣasī	13	Pilipiccha
5	ether				

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	9		13		6		
		4	5	1	3	4	
		3	1	1	5	2	
12		2	2	5	4	4	10
		2	1	3	1	5	
		5	4	3	2	3	
	8		11		7		